

Comparison of Pneumonia Severity Scores in Predicting Mortality among Adult Patients with Pneumonia: An Analytical Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract:**Background:** Community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) remains a significant cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide.**Objectives:** To determine and compare the utility/diagnostic accuracy of pneumonia severity scores (CURB-65, NEWS, NEWS-L, and pneumonia severity index) to predict mortality in patients diagnosed with pneumonia in the emergency department.**Methods:** This was a hospital based analytical cross-sectional study conducted the Department of Emergency Medicine of a tertiary teaching healthcare facility in India between January 2023 and June 2024.**Results:** This study included 210 patients with CAP, with a mortality rate of 10.5%. Non-survivors were older, predominantly female, and had more comorbidities. They exhibited significantly lower systolic and diastolic blood pressure, oxygen saturation, and bicarbonate levels, but higher pulse and respiratory rates, blood urea nitrogen, creatinine, glucose, liver enzymes, sodium, and lactate levels compared to survivors. While haemoglobin, haematocrit, and white blood cell counts were similar between groups, non-survivors had elevated blood glucose, sodium, and lactate levels, and lower blood pH. Mortality prediction scores revealed that non-survivors had significantly higher CURB-65, PSI, NEWS, and NEWS-L scores. Specifically, the NEWS-L score had the highest predictive accuracy, with an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.898, a sensitivity of 85.8%, and a specificity of 96.2%. The NEWS score followed closely with an AUC of 0.890. Both scores outperformed CURB-65 and PSI, highlighting their superior diagnostic accuracy in predicting mortality.**Conclusion:** The study demonstrates that elevated vital signs, biochemical markers, and severity scores are associated with higher mortality in pneumonia patients, with NEWS and NEWS-L providing the most accurate predictions.**Keywords:** Community acquired pneumonia, CURB-65, NEWS, NEWS-L, Pneumonia severity index.

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Introduction

Community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) remains a significant cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide, particularly among older adults and individuals with underlying comorbidities. [1] Despite advancements in antimicrobial therapies and supportive care, CAP continues to impose a substantial burden on healthcare systems, especially in emergency departments where timely and accurate risk stratification is crucial for optimizing patient outcomes. [2] Identifying patients at higher risk of mortality is essential for guiding treatment decisions, such as determining

the appropriate level of care, including the need for intensive care unit (ICU) admission. [3] Several clinical scoring systems have been developed to assess the severity of pneumonia and predict patient outcomes. Among these, the CURB-65 (Confusion, Urea, Respiratory Rate, Blood Pressure, Age ≥ 65 years) score is widely utilized due to its simplicity and effectiveness in stratifying patients based on their risk of mortality. [4] The Pneumonia Severity Index (PSI), which incorporates a broader range of clinical and demographic factors, is another well-established

tool for assessing mortality risk in CAP patients. [5] However, while both CURB-65 and PSI have proven useful, they have limitations, particularly in their ability to predict short-term mortality in patients with severe pneumonia. [6] In recent years, the National Early Warning Score (NEWS) has gained attention for its role in identifying patients at risk of clinical deterioration across various medical conditions, including CAP. NEWS incorporates vital signs and consciousness levels to generate a score that reflects the severity of the patient's condition. [7] An enhanced version of this score, NEWS-L, adds lactate levels, a marker of tissue hypoxia and sepsis, to improve its predictive accuracy. [8] Despite their growing use, there is still a need to compare the effectiveness of these scoring systems directly in predicting mortality among CAP patients, particularly in resource-limited settings. Against this background, the aim of the present study was to determine and compare the utility/diagnostic accuracy of pneumonia severity scores (CURB-65, NEWS, NEWS-L, and pneumonia severity index) to predict mortality in patients diagnosed with pneumonia in the emergency department.

Materials and Methods

This was a hospital based analytical cross-sectional study conducted in the Department of Emergency Medicine of a tertiary teaching healthcare facility in India between January 2023 and June 2024. The study was approved by the Institutional Human Ethics Committee (IHEC). The participants (and their attenders) were given the Participant Information Sheet (PIS) in their native language, and its contents were verbally explained to ensure their understanding and satisfaction. Enrolment into the study proceeded upon receipt of written informed consent. The study included all consecutive patients (nonprobability sampling technique – complete enumeration) more than 18 years of age, of both gender, presenting to/diagnosed with community acquired pneumonia during the prespecified study duration. Patients exhibiting new or aggravated pre-existing infiltrates on chest X-rays, accompanied by at least two symptoms typically associated with pneumonia (such as cough, sputum production, shortness of breath, and pleuritic chest pain) along with notable laboratory findings, were included in the study. Exclusion criteria encompassed individuals with hospital-acquired pneumonia, aspiration pneumonia, pulmonary tuberculosis, pulmonary oedema, and pulmonary thromboembolism.

Kaya et al. (2020) documented the area under the curve to predict mortality among patients with pneumonia to be 0.86 for CURB-65, 0.91 for NEWS, 0.96 for NEWS-L, and 0.71 for PSI. Using this information, considering the level of significance to be 5%, power to be 80% (or 20%

type II error), and attrition rate (non-response rate) to be 10%, the minimum required sample size was computed to be 130 with 95% confidence. However, we enrolled a total of 210 patients in the present study. We used a purpose predesigned, semi structured, pretested proforma to capture the patients' sociodemographic characteristics (including age, gender), detailed clinical history (including comorbidities), findings of general physical examination, systemic examination, vitals (including blood pressure, pulse rate, respiratory rate, temperature), and laboratory parameters (including complete blood count (CBC), renal function tests, liver function tests, arterial blood gas).

The CURB-65 is a clinical tool used to evaluate the severity of community-acquired pneumonia (CAP) and to aid in determining whether a patient should be treated as an inpatient or outpatient. The score is based on five key factors: confusion, elevated blood urea nitrogen levels (≥ 7 mmol/L), a respiratory rate of 30 breaths per minute or higher, low blood pressure (systolic BP < 90 mmHg or diastolic BP ≤ 60 mmHg), and an age of 65 years or older. Each of these factors contributes one point to the overall score, with higher scores indicating more severe disease and a higher risk of mortality. The National Early Warning Score (NEWS) is designed to rapidly identify patients at risk of clinical deterioration, particularly in acute illness. The score is calculated based on respiratory rate, oxygen saturation, systolic blood pressure, pulse rate, level of consciousness (using the AVPU scale), and body temperature. Each parameter is assigned a score from 0 to 3, reflecting the severity of the deviation from normal values. NEWS-L is a modified version of the NEWS score that incorporates lactate levels, which are crucial in detecting sepsis and tissue hypoxia. The Pneumonia Severity Index (PSI), also known as the PORT score, is a comprehensive tool used to assess the mortality risk in patients with community-acquired pneumonia. PSI takes into account a wide range of variables, including demographics (such as age and sex), coexisting medical conditions (like neoplastic disease, liver disease, congestive heart failure, cerebrovascular disease, and renal disease), and physical examination findings (such as altered mental status, respiratory rate, systolic blood pressure, temperature, and pulse). Additionally, PSI considers laboratory and radiographic findings, including arterial pH, blood urea nitrogen, sodium, glucose, haematocrit, pleural effusion, and oxygen levels. The score also accounts for additional risk factors, such as arterial oxygen saturation and partial pressure of oxygen. By assigning points based on these factors, PSI stratifies patients into risk classes, helping to guide treatment decisions and predict the likelihood of mortality. The data obtained was manually entered into Microsoft

Excel and analysed using Stata v16. All the categorical variables were summarised using frequencies and percentages. Continuous variables were summarized using mean (standard deviation) (based on the results of data normality, tested using Kolmogorov–Smirnov test and the Shapiro–Wilk test). To test for statistical significance, Chi square test or Fisher exact test (for categorical variables) and independent “t” test (for continuous variables) was used. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) was used to estimate the area under the curve with 95% confidence and indicators of diagnostic accuracy (including sensitivity and specificity). Statistical significance was considered at p value less than 0.05.

Results

The present study included 210 patients diagnosed with community acquired pneumonia. The mortality rate was found to be 10.5% (22/210 patients). The results showed that the mean age was higher among non-survivors (72.3 ± 15.6 years) compared to survivors (69.2 ± 13.2 years), though the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.308$). Gender distribution was similar, with 68.2% of non-survivors being female, compared to 62.2% of survivors ($p > 0.05$). A significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher proportion of non-survivors had comorbidities (72.7%) compared to survivors (37.2%). Systolic blood pressure (SBP) was significantly lower in non-survivors (100.2 ± 10.5 mmHg) compared to survivors (126.6 ± 20.4 mmHg), with a p-value of < 0.001 . Similarly, diastolic blood pressure (DBP) was lower in non-survivors (61.1 ± 15.4 mmHg) compared to survivors (75.7 ± 15.8 mmHg), also with a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.001$). Non-survivors had a higher pulse rate (116.3 ± 20.4 beats per minute) compared to survivors (93.4 ± 18.8 beats per minute). The respiratory rate was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher in non-survivors (26.2 ± 5.2 breaths per minute) compared to survivors (20.6 ± 4.3 breaths per minute). Body temperature was similar between groups ($37.1 \pm 0.9^\circ\text{C}$ in non-survivors vs. $37.2 \pm 0.7^\circ\text{C}$ in survivors, $p = 0.539$). Oxygen saturation (SPO₂) was significantly lower in non-survivors ($79.2 \pm 11.7\%$) compared to survivors ($90.8 \pm 7.2\%$), with a p-value of < 0.001 .

The mean haemoglobin levels were similar ($p > 0.05$) between non-survivors (11.9 ± 3.1 g/dl) and survivors (12.1 ± 3.9 g/dl). Haematocrit levels were also comparable between the two groups ($39.2 \pm 9.1\%$ in non-survivors vs. $38.8 \pm 7.0\%$ in survivors, $p = 0.806$). White blood cell (WBC) counts were slightly lower in non-survivors ($11,605.3 \pm 5,823.2/\mu\text{l}$) compared to survivors ($12,655.2 \pm 6,544.8/\mu\text{l}$), but this difference was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). However, blood urea nitrogen (BUN) levels were significantly higher in non-survivors (92.6 ± 20.7 mg/dl)

compared to survivors (59.9 ± 30.4 mg/dl), with a p-value of < 0.001 . Similarly, creatinine levels were elevated in non-survivors (2.0 ± 1.2 mg/dl) versus survivors (1.2 ± 0.9 mg/dl), also with a statistically significant difference. Glucose levels were higher in non-survivors (166.5 ± 30.3 mg/dl) compared to survivors (145.8 ± 23.7 mg/dl), with a significant difference. Liver enzymes, including ALT and AST, were markedly elevated in non-survivors (96.4 ± 40.2 IU/l and 110.4 ± 64.2 IU/l, respectively) compared to survivors (33.6 ± 25.6 IU/l and 40.5 ± 30.5 IU/l, respectively), both with p-values of < 0.001 .

Electrolyte analysis showed that sodium levels were higher in non-survivors (140.2 ± 5.4 mmol/l) compared to survivors (136.4 ± 6.3 mmol/l), with a significant difference ($p < 0.05$). Blood pH was lower in non-survivors (7.3 ± 0.3) compared to survivors (7.4 ± 0.2), with a p-value of 0.038. There was no significant difference in pCO₂ levels between the groups (43.2 ± 18.2 kPa in non-survivors vs. 43.3 ± 15.6 kPa in survivors, $p = 0.978$). However, bicarbonate (HCO₃) levels were significantly lower in non-survivors (20.3 ± 5.4 mmol/l) compared to survivors (25.4 ± 1.8 mmol/l), with a p-value of < 0.001 . Lactate levels were significantly higher in non-survivors (5.4 ± 2.9 mmol/l) compared to survivors (2.3 ± 1.4 mmol/l), with a p-value of < 0.001 .

The mean (SD) CURB-65 scores among survivors was 2.0 (0.7) and that among non-survivors was 3.2 (0.8) – the difference (higher scores among non-survivors) was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The mean (SD) pneumonia severity index scores were 122.1 (24.3) among survivors and 140.0 (22.2) among non-survivors – the difference (higher scores among non-survivors) was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The mean (SD) NEWS scores among survivors was 5.4 (2.5) and that among non-survivors was 10.9 (3.0) – the difference (higher scores among non-survivors) was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The mean (SD) NEWS-L scores among survivors was 7.8 (3.1) and that among non-survivors was 16.1 (3.1) – the difference (higher scores among non-survivors) was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

For the CURB-65 score, a vast majority of non-survivors (86.4%) were classified as Class 3, compared to only 18.6% of survivors ($p < 0.05$). In contrast, most survivors were classified as Class 2 (57.4%), while only 9.1% of non-survivors fell into this category. A small proportion of non-survivors (4.5%) were in Class 1, compared to 23.9% of survivors. The PSI score also showed marked differences, with 50.0% of non-survivors being in Class 5, compared to 25.0% of survivors ($p < 0.05$). Conversely, a larger proportion of survivors (61.2%) were in Class 4, while only 45.5% of non-

survivors were in this class. Very few patients were classified in the lower classes, with 4.5% of non-survivors and 4.3% of survivors in Class 1, and even fewer in Classes 2 and 3. The NEWS also differed significantly between groups. A striking 95.5% of non-survivors were in Class 3, compared to 37.8% of survivors ($p < 0.05$). For NEWS-L, all non-survivors (100%) were classified in the highest risk category, Class 4, while this was true for only 48.4% of survivors ($p < 0.05$). None of the non-survivors fell into the lower classes (1-3), while a significant portion of survivors did. The CURB-65 score demonstrated an AUC of 0.867 with a cut-off value of greater than 2, yielding a sensitivity of 84.2% and a specificity of 80.4%, with a

statistically significant p-value of < 0.001 . The PSI score had an AUC of 0.787 and a cut-off value of greater than 136, with a sensitivity of 68.2% and a specificity of 74.5%, also statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). The NEWS score showed a higher predictive value with an AUC of 0.890 and a cut-off value of greater than 7, achieving a sensitivity of 94.7% and a specificity of 78.4%, with a p-value of < 0.001 . The NEWS-L score had the highest AUC at 0.898 with a cut-off value of greater than 13.8, demonstrating a sensitivity of 85.8% and a specificity of 96.2%, with a p-value of < 0.001 . These findings indicate that NEWS and NEWS-L have superior predictive accuracy for patient outcomes compared to CURB-65 and PSI.

Table 1: Comparison of non-survivors and survivors, by sociodemographic variables and vitals

		Non survivors N = 22	Survivors N = 188	Total N = 210	P value
		Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	
Age (in years)		72.3 (15.6)	69.2 (13.2)	141.5	0.308
Gender n (%)	Female	15 (68.2)	117 (62.2)	132 (62.9)	0.585
	Male	7 (31.8)	71 (37.8)	78 (37.1)	
Comorbidity n (%)	Present	16 (72.7)	70 (37.2)	86 (40.9)	0.001*
	Absent	6 (27.3)	118 (62.8)	124 (59.1)	
SBP (in mmHg)		100.2 (10.5)	126.6 (20.4)	113.4 (15.5)	$< 0.001^*$
DBP (in mmHg)		61.1 (15.4)	75.7 (15.8)	68.4 (15.6)	0.001*
Pulse rate (per min)		116.3 (20.4)	93.4 (18.8)	104.9 (19.6)	$< 0.001^*$
Respiratory rate (per min)		26.2 (5.2)	20.6 (4.3)	23.4 (4.8)	$< 0.001^*$
Body temperature (C)		37.1 (0.9)	37.2 (0.7)	37.2 (0.8)	0.539
SPO2 (%)		79.2 (11.7)	90.8 (7.2)	85.0 (9.5)	$< 0.001^*$

*Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 2: Comparison of non-survivors and survivors, by laboratory parameters

		Non survivors N = 22	Survivors N = 188	Total N = 210	P value
		Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	
Haemoglobin (gm/dl)		11.9 (3.1)	12.1 (3.9)	12.0 (3.5)	0.817
Haematocrit (%)		39.2 (9.1)	38.8 (7.0)	39.0 (8.1)	0.806
WBC (μ l)		11605.3 (5823.2)	12655.2 (6544.8)	12130.3 (6184.0)	0.473
Blood urea nitrogen (mg/dl)		92.6 (20.7)	59.9 (30.4)	76.3 (25.6)	$< 0.001^*$
Creatinine (mg/dl)		2.0 (1.2)	1.2 (0.9)	1.6 (1.1)	$< 0.001^*$
Glucose (mg/dl)		166.5 (30.3)	145.8 (23.7)	156.2 (27.0)	$< 0.001^*$
ALT (IU/l)		96.4 (40.2)	33.6 (25.6)	65.0 (32.9)	$< 0.001^*$
AST (IU/l)		110.4 (64.2)	40.5 (30.5)	75.5 (47.4)	$< 0.001^*$
Sodium (mmol/l)		140.2 (5.4)	136.4 (6.3)	138.3 (5.9)	0.007*
pH		7.3 (0.3)	7.4 (0.2)	7.4 (0.1)	0.038*
pCO2 (kPa)		43.2 (18.2)	43.3 (15.6)	43.3 (16.9)	0.978
pO2 (kPa)		48.2 (20.2)	57.3 (24.5)	52.8 (22.4)	0.095
HCO3 (mmol/l)		20.3 (5.4)	25.4 (1.8)	22.9 (3.6)	$< 0.001^*$
Lactate (mmol/l)		5.4 (2.9)	2.3 (1.4)	3.9 (2.2)	$< 0.001^*$

*Statistically significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 3: Comparison of non-survivors and survivors, by pneumonia severity scores

		Non survivors N = 22	Survivors N = 188	Total N = 210	P value
		n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	
CURB-65	Class 1	1 (4.5)	45 (23.9)	46 (21.9)	$< 0.001^*$
	Class 2	2 (9.1)	108 (57.4)	110 (52.4)	

	Class 3	19 (86.4)	35 (18.6)	54 (25.7)	
PSI	Class 1	1 (4.5)	8 (4.3)	9 (4.3)	<0.001*
	Class 2	0 (0.0)	4 (2.1)	4 (1.9)	
	Class 3	0 (0.0)	14 (7.4)	14 (6.7)	
	Class 4	10 (45.5)	115 (61.2)	125 (59.5)	
	Class 5	11 (50.0)	47 (25.0)	58 (27.6)	
NEWS	Class 1	0 (0.0)	66 (35.1)	66 (31.4)	<0.001*
	Class 2	1 (4.5)	51 (27.1)	52 (24.8)	
	Class 3	21 (95.5)	71 (37.8)	92 (43.8)	
NEWS-L	Class 1	0 (0.0)	13 (6.9)	13 (6.2)	0.003*
	Class 2	0 (0.0)	32 (17.0)	32 (15.2)	
	Class 3	0 (0.0)	52 (27.7)	52 (24.8)	
	Class 4	22 (100)	91 (48.4)	113 (53.8)	

*Statistically significant at p<0.05

Table 4: Receiver operating characteristic analysis of pneumonia severity scores to predict mortality

	AUC	Cut off	Sensitivity	Specificity	P value
CURB-65	0.867	>2	84.2	80.4	<0.001*
PSI	0.787	>136	68.2	74.5	<0.001*
NEWS	0.890	>7	94.7	78.4	<0.001*
NEWS-L	0.898	>13.8	85.8	96.2	<0.001*

*Statistically significant at p<0.05

Figure 1: Receiver operating characteristic analysis of pneumonia severity scores to predict mortality

Discussion

The aim of the present study was to determine and compare the utility/diagnostic accuracy of pneumonia severity scores (CURB-65, NEWS, NEWS-L, and pneumonia severity index) to predict mortality in patients diagnosed with pneumonia in the emergency department. Among the 210 patients included in the study, the mortality rate was found to be 10.5%. This finding is consistent with

previous studies, which have reported mortality rates for CAP ranging from 5% to 15% depending on the population studied and the severity of the disease at presentation (Fine et al., 1997; Musher & Thorner, 2014). [9,10] the analysis revealed that the mean age was higher among non-survivors compared to survivors, although this difference was not statistically significant.

Advanced age has been consistently identified as a risk factor for increased mortality in CAP patients. Previous research by Marrie et al.[11] (1989) and Ewig et al.[12] (2009) highlighted that elderly patients are more likely to succumb to pneumonia due to decreased physiological reserves and a higher likelihood of comorbidities. However, the lack of statistical significance in the present study may be due to the relatively small sample size or the distribution of other mortality-associated factors that might mitigate the impact of age alone. The gender distribution was similar between the two groups, with 68.2% of non-survivors being female compared to 62.2% of survivors. Historically, gender differences in pneumonia outcomes have been variable, with some studies suggesting that males are more prone to severe disease, while others report higher mortality rates in females, particularly in older age groups (Kaplan et al., 2002).[13] A significant finding in this study was the higher prevalence of comorbidities among non-survivors (72.7%) compared to survivors (37.2%). Comorbid conditions such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), heart failure, diabetes mellitus, and chronic kidney disease have been well-documented to adversely affect the prognosis of patients with CAP (Musher & Thorner, 2014; Restrepo et al., 2010).[10,14] These comorbidities likely contribute to worse outcomes by compromising the immune response and increasing the risk of complications, such as septic shock and respiratory failure.

SBP and DBP were both significantly lower in non-survivors than in survivors. Hypotension is a well-known predictor of poor outcomes in CAP, often reflecting severe sepsis or septic shock, which are associated with high mortality rates (Fine et al., 1999; Lim et al., 2003).[15,16] The significant difference in blood pressure between survivors and non-survivors in this study underscores the importance of early recognition and management of hypotension in CAP patients. The study also found that non-survivors had significantly higher pulse rates and respiratory rates compared to survivors. Tachycardia and tachypnoea are critical signs of systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) and have been associated with increased mortality in CAP (Renaud et al., 2009).[17] These findings are consistent with the understanding that elevated heart and respiratory rates reflect a body's compensatory mechanisms to maintain oxygen delivery in the face of severe infection and hypoxemia. Oxygen saturation (SPO₂) was markedly lower in non-survivors compared to survivors. Hypoxemia is a direct consequence of impaired gas exchange in the lungs due to inflammation and consolidation in pneumonia. Previous studies have shown that low SPO₂ levels on admission are strongly predictive of poor outcomes, including mortality, in CAP patients

(Bilben et al., 2016).[18] The substantial difference in oxygen saturation between survivors and non-survivors in this study highlights the critical need for prompt oxygen therapy and possibly more aggressive respiratory support in patients presenting with low SPO₂ levels. The study found no significant difference in haemoglobin levels between non-survivors and survivors. Similarly, haematocrit levels were comparable between the two groups. These findings suggest that anemia or variations in red blood cell concentration do not significantly impact mortality in CAP patients. This aligns with previous studies, such as those by Espinoza et al. (2019),[19] which found that while anemia is common in critically ill patients, its presence alone is not a strong predictor of mortality in CAP. WBC counts were slightly lower in non-survivors than in survivors, though this difference was not statistically significant. Leucocytosis is a common response to infection; however, the lack of a significant difference in WBC counts between the two groups may indicate that the body's immune response, as reflected by WBC count, does not necessarily correlate with mortality.[20] This finding is consistent with research suggesting that other factors, such as the nature of the immune response and the presence of comorbidities, may play a more crucial role in determining outcomes in CAP (Gogos et al., 2000).[21] The study revealed that BUN levels were significantly higher in non-survivors compared to survivors. Elevated BUN is a well-established marker of poor outcomes in patients with CAP and is a key component of the CURB-65 severity score (Lim et al., 2003).[16] The increase in BUN levels in non-survivors likely reflects both dehydration and renal impairment, which are common in severe infections and are associated with worse prognoses.[22]

Creatinine levels were also significantly elevated in non-survivors, further corroborating the association between renal dysfunction and increased mortality risk in CAP patients. The study found that glucose levels were significantly higher in non-survivors compared to survivors. Hyperglycaemia in the context of infection has been widely documented as a predictor of adverse outcomes, particularly in patients with sepsis (Finfer et al., 2009).[23] Elevated glucose levels may reflect a stress response to infection, with higher levels indicating a more severe systemic response. Hyperglycaemia can impair immune function and is associated with an increased risk of complications such as secondary infections and septic shock, which could explain the higher mortality observed in patients with elevated glucose levels. Liver enzyme levels, specifically alanine transaminase (ALT) and aspartate transaminase (AST), were markedly elevated in non-survivors compared to survivors. This finding is significant as it suggests that hepatic dysfunction may be a critical factor in the

progression of severe CAP. Liver dysfunction in CAP can occur due to direct viral or bacterial infection, sepsis-induced hepatic ischemia, or as a result of multi-organ failure (Pugh et al., 1973).[24] The elevation of liver enzymes in non-survivors could indicate a higher degree of systemic inflammation and organ dysfunction, contributing to the higher mortality observed in this group. Sodium levels were significantly higher in non-survivors, which could indicate dehydration or the presence of hypernatremia, both of which are associated with worse outcomes in critically ill patients (Arampatzis et al., 2012).[25] The study also found that blood pH was lower in non-survivors, reflecting a state of acidosis. Acidosis, particularly metabolic acidosis, is often a sign of severe illness and is associated with increased mortality in CAP (Chand et al., 2022).[26] The significantly lower HCO₃ levels in non-survivors further support the presence of metabolic acidosis, which could be due to renal failure, respiratory failure, or sepsis. Perhaps one of the most striking findings of the study was the significantly higher lactate levels in non-survivors compared to survivors. Elevated lactate is a well-known marker of tissue hypoxia and is strongly associated with increased mortality in various conditions, including sepsis and CAP (Mikkelsen et al., 2009).[27] Lactate levels rise when oxygen delivery to tissues is insufficient to meet metabolic demands, often due to severe sepsis or shock. The substantial difference in lactate levels between the two groups underscores the importance of this marker in assessing the severity of CAP and predicting outcomes.

The CURB-65 score is widely used for its simplicity and effectiveness in assessing the severity of CAP. The AUC for CURB-65 was 0.867, with a cut-off value greater than 2 yielding a sensitivity of 84.2% and a specificity of 80.4%. These findings align with previous studies that have demonstrated CURB-65's effectiveness in predicting adverse outcomes, though it is not without limitations. For instance, Myint et al.[28] (2005) pointed out that while CURB-65 is useful in determining the need for hospitalization, it may not be as robust in predicting mortality in patients with underlying comorbidities, which could explain the relatively lower specificity observed in this study. The PSI score, while more comprehensive, did not perform as well as the CURB-65 in this study. Half of the non-survivors were in the highest risk category (Class 5), compared to 25% of survivors, with a statistically significant difference. The AUC for PSI was 0.787, with a sensitivity of 68.2% and a specificity of 74.5% at a cut-off value of greater than 136. Despite its comprehensive nature, incorporating a wide range of variables, the PSI score's predictive accuracy was lower than that of CURB-65, NEWS, and NEWS-L. This may be due

to the complexity of the PSI, which includes factors such as age and comorbidities that may not directly correlate with acute mortality risk but rather long-term prognosis (Aujesky et al., 2005).[29] The NEWS score demonstrated superior predictive value, with an AUC of 0.890 and a cut-off value greater than 7, achieving a sensitivity of 94.7% and a specificity of 78.4%. A striking 95.5% of non-survivors were classified as high risk (Class 3), compared to 37.8% of survivors. This high sensitivity makes NEWS an excellent tool for early identification of critically ill patients who may benefit from intensive monitoring and intervention (Smith et al., 2013).[30] The slightly lower specificity compared to NEWS-L suggests that while NEWS is effective in identifying at-risk patients, it may also flag some patients who do not ultimately experience adverse outcomes. However, the balance of high sensitivity with reasonable specificity makes NEWS particularly valuable in emergency settings where the priority is to prevent mortality. The NEWS-L score, which incorporates lactate levels into the standard NEWS, demonstrated the highest predictive accuracy in this study, with an AUC of 0.898, a sensitivity of 85.8%, and a specificity of 96.2% at a cut-off value greater than 13.8. All non-survivors were classified in the highest risk category (Class 4). Lactate is a well-known indicator of tissue hypoxia and sepsis, conditions that significantly increase mortality risk in CAP (Shapiro et al., 2005).[31] The inclusion of lactate levels in the NEWS score enhances its predictive accuracy, particularly in identifying patients with severe sepsis who are at high risk of death.

Conclusion

The present study provides valuable insights into the comparative utility and diagnostic accuracy of four pneumonia severity scores—CURB-65, PSI, NEWS, and NEWS-L—in predicting mortality among patients with community-acquired pneumonia in an emergency department setting. The findings demonstrate that while all four scoring systems are useful, NEWS and NEWS-L, in particular, exhibit superior predictive accuracy. NEWS-L, which incorporates lactate levels, emerged as the most reliable tool, with the highest sensitivity and specificity, making it an excellent option for identifying high-risk patients who may benefit from more intensive monitoring and intervention.

Given its ease of use and strong prognostic performance, NEWS-L should be considered for integration into clinical protocols for managing pneumonia in emergency settings, where timely and accurate risk stratification is crucial.

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